

USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: In this article, I am going to write about using interactive methods and their benefits in learning foreign languages, I hope that it will be beneficial for all people who are learning languages or interested in learning them quickly using these methods.

The main purpose to write this article is to give more information about types of interactive methods and their usages in order to learn or teach languages more productive and well qualified. Furthermore, I really want to help learners to make easier learning foreign languages by making fun.

Key words: Interactive methods, advantages of interactive methods, educational tool, learning languages, role-play activities, brainstorming method, case-study method, presentations.

The rapid evolution of renewed society forces students learning and realizing materials quickly, especially a foreign language. These days, mastery at least one foreign language becomes an important requirement for professional specialist competence. Accordingly, it is compulsory to pay attention to the productivity and quality of learning foreign language. Therefore, the most effective methods of learning foreign language are interactive methods.

The main term "interactive" means that an exchange of ideas where both participants are active and can effect on one another. Therefore, interactive methods are an organization of learning process, in which it is impossible for students not to participate in a collective. [1, p.159]. Interactive methods of teaching foreign languages help students exchange information, which they know or gain from the lessons. This process is very beneficial for extravert learners, as they do not recite their ideas, opinions with others. Therefore, interactive methods

help them to overcome these disadvantages. Additionally, during exchanging datas, they can also gain practical communication skills in the language they are studying. Furthermore, learners can also benefit in supportive relationship. It means that, students participate in lessons with their group or partner. In the classes they compete with other members of group and support each other. In this situation they realize that supporting each other is a vital thing during activities. Interactive methods also develop critical thinking, analytical skills, abilities to search, find and process new information and finally make decisions grounded with the necessary arguments. Other advantage of this method is developing child's creativity and individual thinking manner, because teacher who encourages every student to participate in the process of group discussion and the entire learning process.

The most popular methods are role plays, brainstorming, discussions, case-study methods and presentations. They develop communicative skills, logical thinking and different types of intellectual activity such as analysis, synthesis, comparison and generalization [2, p. 30].

1. Role-play activities give students the opportunity to assume the role of a person or act out a given situation. These roles can be performed by individual students, in pairs or in groups which can play out a more complex scenario.[3, www.niu.edu]. There are two wide types of role-play activities. They are scripted and non-scripted role-plays. With a scripted role-play, the teacher might use an example in a text book. Non-scripted ones are such role-plays when students are given some roles and should use whatever knowledge they have in order to speak with partner. Role-play method is especially beneficial in developing language. In this stage students allowed to demonstrate their ability. They independently explore their given topic and by this they learn more information and words about the topic. Additionally role-play enables better teamwork and communication. Also, it is fun, so learners learn more when they have fun while learning. Role-play activities develop not only language but also abilities including communication, acting, how to behave among others and do not be shy to act.

2. Brainstorming is a group problem-solving method that involves the spontaneous contribution of creative ideas and solutions. This technique requires intensive, freewheeling discussion in which every member of group is encouraged to think aloud and suggest as many ideas as possible, based on their diverse knowledge [4, www.techtarget.com]. During the classes students should be divided into two or more groups and teacher gives them brainstorming tasks

like mind mapping. A mind map is a visually connected form of new and related ideas which radiate out from the central theme. Students need papers or whiteboard and markers. Teacher gives them central topic and set a timer. They should write as much words as they can which are related to the main topic. At the end of the task winner group is determined by the numbers of new and related ideas to the theme. Brainstorming is effective in writing skills also. It helps students generate more ideas before writing a topic in a short period of time. Moreover, brainstorming improves our memory. For instance, when someone combines some facts and ideas in different groups, he/she can easily come up with creative solutions to problems. Additionally, brainstorming challenges learners to generate not only one, but various solutions for a problem.

3. Another accessible interactive method is discussion. Discussion-based learning is a learning style that challenges students to be responsible for their own education. Students are required to sit around oval- discussion table and they are asked to find new information together, talk, wait for answers and think for themselves. [5, www.beaconacademy.ph]. In this stage happen exchanging ideas among a teacher and students. There are many types of discussion, like class discussion, panel discussion, symposium and colloquium. A class discussion can be on a specific topic such as Global warming. Panel discussion is also known as a round table discussion. In this type of discussion students express their opinions on a given problem. In the symposium students present their opinions, understandings on a given subject. It also provides learners an experience in public speaking. Colloquium type consist of two groups, one of experts or specialists and the other of students. Advantage of discussion based-learning is that it is more interactive than a lecture. In the lecture only teacher explains, talks and it is too boring for students to listen. When they discuss topic with a group, they may participate in classes more and also by thinking, discussing they can widen their outlook also.

4. A presentation is an explanation or a talk about a new product, plan to a group. In this method teacher gives to a student or a group the topic, which students should present it during the classes. Mostly students use PPT (Microsoft PowerPoint) to explain their theme. They use their laptops to create them and add only essential data or notes about topic. Presentation method is beneficial for present something easily and maintain eye contact with a large audience by showing the slides with a keyword. Additionally, learners by presenting them can

be stimulated by a good lecturer. By this they can identify about how to be a good and experienced lecturer.

5. A case study is a process of research in order to learn a subject, an event or an organization. The case-study method mostly involves three steps. Step 1: The teacher introduces new theme and vocabulary related to the topic. Step 2: Everyone reads the case study and analyzes additional materials. Step 3: Students discuss possible solutions, usually in small groups. A major advantage of teaching with case-study method is that the students are actively engaged in figuring out the principles by abstracting from the examples. This develops their skills in problem solving. Additionally, it develops learners' ability to realize and distinguish between critical and extraneous factors. Case studies provide students with scenarios in which they can begin to think about their understanding and solutions to problems found in real-world situations.

Knowing some languages is major for getting a good job, for travelling and of course for getting into university. Especially, in our country, when somebody wants to find well-paid job, it will be beneficial them to know at least two foreign languages. In this case, interactive methods are useful in learning them more quickly and also well qualified. With these methods learners not only learn something and bored, but also they have fun doing activities related to topics. In this article I gave some common types of interactive methods that one can use them during their classes without any distraction. I think they will be helpful and encourage us to learn more languages as possible as we can.

REFERENCES:

1. Каминская Е.В. Разнообразие современных интерактивных методов обучения иностранному языку в ВУЗе / Е.В. Каминская// Язык и мир изучаемого языка. Вып.7. Саратов: Саратовский социально-экономический институт (филиал) РЭУ им. Г.В.Плеханова, 2016.- С. 159-165.
2. Пометун.О.І., Сучасний урок. Інтерактивні технології навчання: наук. - метод. посібник / І.О.Пометун, Л.В. Пироженко. - Київ: 2006.- 30 с.
3. www.niu.edu
4. www.techtarget.com
5. www.beaconacademy.ph